

A Training and Test Error for Synthetic Problems

Figures 11-14 display the median training and test error of the best individual (measured on the entire training data) found so far over generations for tournament and ϵ -lexicase selection respectively for the synthetic Friedman problems with varying degrees of noise or varying numbers of features. Both selection methods are also displayed with different down-sampling techniques. For better readability the graphs are smoothed using a moving average with a window of 20 generations and markers are added every 200 generations.

Similar to our results in Sect. 4.1 and Sect. 4.2 we observe that down-sampling improves both performance and generalization behavior for tournament and ϵ -lexicase selection on the synthetic Friedman problems. This effect is more notable for larger problem sizes.

Figures 15-18 show the test error and the generalization gap including outliers for the synthetic Friedman problems with varying degrees of noise or varying numbers of features. Especially for the FRIEDMAN2 and FRIEDMAN3 problem, we observe a few runs with high outlier values.

Fig. 11. Median training and test fitness over generations of tournament selection with nds, rds, and ids for the synthetic problems across different noise levels. Median over 30 runs is shown.

Fig. 12. Median training and test fitness over generations of ϵ -lexicase selection with nds, rds, and ids for the synthetic problems across different noise levels. Median over 30 runs is shown.

Fig. 13. Median training and test fitness over generations of tournament selection with nds, rds, and ids for the synthetic FRIEDMAN1 problem with varying numbers of features (5, 10, 25, 50). Median over 30 runs is shown.

Fig. 14. Median training and test fitness over generations of ϵ -lexicase selection with nds, rds, and ids for the synthetic FRIEDMAN1 problem with varying numbers of features (5, 10, 25, 50). Median over 30 runs is shown.

Fig. 15. Test fitness of the best individual for the synthetic problems across different noise levels. Outliers are shown.

Fig. 16. Generalization gap between test and training fitness of the best individual for the synthetic problems across different noise levels. Outliers are shown.

Fig. 17. Test fitness of the best individual for the synthetic FRIEDMAN1 problem with varying numbers of features (5, 10, 25, 50). Outliers are shown.

Fig. 18. Generalization gap between test and training fitness of the best individual for the synthetic FRIEDMAN1 problem with varying numbers of features (5, 10, 25, 50). Outliers are shown.

B Training and Test Error for Real-World Problems

Figures 19 and 20 display the median training and test error of the best individual (measured on the entire training data) found so far over generations for tournament and ϵ -lexicase selection for the real-world problems. Both selection methods are also displayed with different down-sampling techniques. For better readability the graphs are smoothed using a moving average with a window of 20 generations and markers are added every 200 generations.

Confirming the results in Sect. 4.3 we observe that down-sampling helps more for the two larger problems and tournament selection with down-sampling performs better compared to ϵ -lexicase with down-sampling for larger problem sizes.

Figures 21 and 22 show the test error and the generalization gap including outliers for the real-world problems. For all real-world problems, there was at least one run with a large outlier.

Fig. 19. Median training and test fitness over generations of tournament selection with nds, rds, and ids for the real-world problems. Median over 30 runs is shown.

Fig. 20. Median training and test fitness over generations of ϵ -lexicase selection with nds, rds, and ids for the real-world problems. Median over 30 runs is shown.

Fig. 21. Test fitness of the best individual for the real-world problems. Outliers are shown.

Fig. 22. Generalization gap between training and test fitness of the best individual for the real-world problems. Outliers are shown.

C Diversity and Size for Synthetic Problems with varying Numbers of Features

Figure 23 displays the diversity over generations for the different selection methods on varying sizes of the synthetic FRIEDMAN1 problem. Similar, to the results in Sect. 4.1 we observe that down-sampling improves the diversity of tournament to the level of ϵ -lexicase selection. We do not observe a change of this trend with changing problem size. Further, we observe the same code growth control by down-sampling for different problem sizes as before in Sect. 4.1.

Fig. 23. Error diversity of individuals in a population over generations for the synthetic FRIEDMAN1 problem with varying numbers of features (5, 10, 25, 50). Median over 30 runs is shown.

Fig. 24. Median size of individuals in a population (measured in tree nodes) over generations for the synthetic FRIEDMAN1 problem with varying numbers of features (5, 10, 25, 50). Median over 30 runs is shown.

D Statistical Analysis

We performed a statistical analysis of the results to test for significant differences in the performance of the methods. We used the Wilcoxon rank-sum test and applied a Holm-correction due to multiple comparisons. We set the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$.

Tables 3-5 show the median MSE on the test cases for all methods on the Friedman problems with varying degrees of noise, the FRIEDMAN1 problem with varying size and the real-world problems, respectively. Significant improvements with respect to another method are indicated by the methods labels ($a - f$).

On the FRIEDMAN2 and FRIEDMAN3 problem, informed down-sampled tournament selection significantly outperforms tournament selection without down-sampling. However, there are only a few significant differences between the down-sampled variants of ϵ -lexicase selection and tournament selection. On the FRIEDMAN2 problem, informed down-sampled ϵ -lexicase selection significantly outperforms random down-sampled tournament selection for two noise levels. On the FRIEDMAN1 problem with 5 or 10 features informed down-sampled ϵ -lexicase selection performs significantly worse than other selection methods.

The statistical analysis for the real-world problems shows that there are only significant differences for the MACHINE_CPU and TECATOR datasets. On the MACHINE_CPU dataset, random down-sampled ϵ -lexicase selection significantly outperforms informed down-sampled tournament selection. On the TECATOR dataset, tournament selection and ϵ -lexicase selection combined with informed down-sampling significantly outperform the other ϵ -lexicase variants.

Table 3. Median MSE on the test cases for all methods on synthetic Friedman problems across different noise levels. A significant improvement with respect to another method is indicated by the method labels. Best results are highlighted in bold. The results are rounded to two decimal places.

	friedman1				friedman2				friedman3			
	0.00	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.00	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.00	0.05	0.10	0.15
^a nds-tourn	3.58	3.16	3.85	4.30	89.43	59.41	47.87	83.27	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.04
^b rds-tourn	^f 3.32	3.62	3.57	3.77	11.38	5.80	11.96	7.67	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.04
^c ids-tourn	4.95	4.24	4.52	3.37	^a 3.59	^a 6.31	^a 3.52	^a 1.78	^a 0.01	^a 0.00	^a 0.01	0.04
^d nds- ϵ -lex	4.04	3.83	4.66	4.15	^a 0.93	^a 3.18	^a 1.68	^a 0.76	^a 0.01	0.03	^a 0.04	0.06
^e rds- ϵ -lex	4.08	3.63	4.45	3.82	^a 7.15	7.14	^a 1.56	^a 4.10	^a 0.01	^a 0.01	0.01	0.04
^f ids- ϵ -lex	4.96	4.54	5.06	4.84	^{ab} 0.56	^a 0.78	^{ab} 1.79	^a 1.44	^a 0.01	0.02	0.04	0.05

Table 4. Median MSE on the test cases for all methods on the FRIEDMAN1 problem with varying numbers of features (5, 10, 25, 50). A significant improvement with respect to another method is indicated by the label. Best results are highlighted in bold. The results are rounded to two decimal places.

	friedman1_5	friedman1_10	friedman1_25	friedman1_50
^a nds-tourn	^f 1.21	3.58	6.38	7.08
^b rds-tourn	^f 1.21	^f 3.32	5.11	6.28
^c ids-tourn	3.03	4.95	5.35	5.61
^d nds- ϵ -lex	^{cf} 1.11	4.04	6.20	8.49
^e rds- ϵ -lex	^f 1.58	4.08	5.71	6.01
^f ids- ϵ -lex	3.51	4.96	6.23	7.19

Table 5. Median MSE on the test cases for all methods on the real-world problems. A significant improvement with respect to another method is indicated by the label. Best results are highlighted in bold. The results are rounded to two decimal places.

	210_cloud	230_machine_cpu	207_autoPrice	505_tecator
^a nds-tourn	0.31	6128.11	9875451.10	10.26
^b rds-tourn	0.36	4991.18	6947265.06	11.92
^c ids-tourn	0.28	7228.54	8423416.78	^{bde} 7.17
^d nds- ϵ -lex	0.29	3908.10	8247862.92	13.41
^e rds- ϵ -lex	0.25	^c 3412.84	7382951.41	12.53
^f ids- ϵ -lex	0.29	4001.97	9096126.31	^{de} 8.40